

Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

D1.2 Interim Data Management Plan

WP1: Management

30 June 2025 / v1.0

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1. Executive Summary

FOCCUS provides products to both internal and external users. The data workflow is based on a chain of individual operational components, each contributing either to data production or user interaction functions. The infrastructure implements open and free of charge data access, it adopts international standards, follows European regulations such as INSPIRE, it is accessible under the FOCCUS web domain (<https://foccus-project.eu/>) and offers up-to-date means of data and data products dissemination and interaction tools.

Nevertheless, the developed system cannot be considered finally closed, and for the entire duration of the project, the following evolution principles have to be considered and applied:

- The service shall be state-of-the-art in its scope, and it shall be user-driven.

This means that all service capabilities are defined, allocated and implemented with sound and state-of-the-art technical and scientific justifications and address FOCCUS internal and external user needs. If new needs pop up, it is important to try and match (whenever possible) these new needs.

Providing international level state-of-the-art tools means a constant monitoring and application of most appropriate methodologies at a given time to meet requirements for service quality in data processing, validation, etc.

- Common standards are adopted and applied throughout the different elements of the system.

This means that standards are identified, adopted and applied. If, during the lifetime of the project, rising ocean best practices (OBP) become standards, the project has to try and include (as much as possible) these new OBP.

This also means that the system evolves constantly in response to service requirements, scientific and technical requirements, marine environment products requirements, and stakeholders' requirements.

- Quality of the methodology of workflow has to follow and apply well-established engineering methodologies derived from industry (es. ISO9001:2015, ISO15288, etc.) and drive the definition of an adapted approach.

This means that data management also adopts good practices and methodologies to ensure system monitoring, fixing and reporting.

Within this framework, FOCCUS poses itself as up-to-date in terms of data infrastructure, adopts the latest interoperability best practices, and enables data products FAIRness to maximise the FOCCUS data value chain from production to its consumption.

2. Scope of the Document

This document presents the interim version of the Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean for Copernicus users (FOCCUS) Data Management Plan (DMP) and it is based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan (DMP) template. FOCCUS moves beyond open access in implementing open science practices while following Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR) principles. It applies to research data collected and produced during the project, as well as to publications.

All observational data and derived products are made freely available via EU public data repositories, and a data management strategy is implemented (WP1) for providing immediate and free access to collected data. Besides adopting open data management software tools and supporting INSPIRE themes (e.g. European harmonised and controlled vocabularies), FOCCUS contributes to the development of needed extensions and shares these outcomes via open repositories (e.g. Zenodo, GitHub, StackOverflow, Open Science Framework (OSF)) and repositories of partner institutes. Project developed data management software tools are made freely available under creative commons/open data commons licensing.

The document recalls the scope of the FOCCUS project and describes the FOCCUS framework for the research data management according to the requirements of article 17 and analysed in the Annotated Grant Agreement, article 17. These include: description of data (data summary), approach to FAIRness, research outputs, allocation of resources, security and ethics.

Document Disclaimers:

This document is based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template [V1.0 May 2021] and adapted to provide the FOCCUS partners and FOCCUS stakeholders a living guide for the project Data Management Plan. The Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of the content of this publication

3. Data Summary

The coastal zones are the most heavily used and impacted areas of the global ocean, as a consequence of large concentration of the human population inhabiting coastal areas, high number of human activities, and diverse array of resulting human pressures and anthropogenic stressors (e.g., pollution, eutrophication, poor water quality, degradation of coastal ecosystems and habitats).

Copernicus Marine Service is already providing key data and information on the coastal zone, however the use of Earth Observation (EO) data for coastal monitoring and forecasting is not explored enough, thereby the objective of FOCCUS is to address and enhance the coastal extension of the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) to

better serve coastal users and Member States (MS), and to develop advanced and seamless coastal monitoring and forecasting systems.

This is essential and timely so that the existing CMEMS can evolve as a key coastal data and information service for Europe, working in collaboration with the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) to ensure optimised and interoperable in situ data provision, to provide the high quality, trusted, marine knowledge needed for evidence-based management and protection of the coastal zones. Lately, Copernicus launched the Copernicus Coastal Hub (<https://www.coastal.hub.copernicus.eu/>) with the aim of offering a single shop hub that provides coastal data and information to support evidence-based decision-making and promote sustainable management practices for coastal ecosystems. The Copernicus Coastal Hub includes all the services that draw from satellite Earth Observation and in-situ (non-space) data, and FOCCUS is aiming at being a pillar in the development of such a service.

In this framework, timely, free and unrestricted exchange of marine and coastal observational data is essential for empowering decision makers with evidence-based information for sustainable management of the very dynamic and complex coastal environment.

Moreover, considering that coastal zone monitoring and processes are coupled with clear policy drivers that require MS to monitor and assess, manage and protect their national waters in order to meet important EU policies (e.g., MSFD, WFD, MSPD, CFP) and wider policy initiatives (e.g., the European Green Deal) and the Horizon Europe Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters, an open and free data policy and support for data interoperability are mandatory actions.

Notably, interoperability of data systems has become a priority with the development of FAIR principles (2014) (<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>), a set of guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship (Wilkinson et al., 2016) was developed to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable.

The availability and accessibility of coastal data is not always easy and often the sources are lacking compliance to international standards, such as using different formats, wide diversity of datasets, and disparate data management structures, among others (Tanhua et al., 2019 described this issue for oceanographic data but it applies well to coastal zones too).

With this background in mind, this document describes the FOCCUS Data Management Plan (DMP). More specifically it describes how the research data collected during the project will be managed to move beyond the FAIR concepts and how users would be able to have immediate and free access to collected data.

3.1 Purpose of Data Generation/Reuse

The objective of FOCCUS is to address and enhance the coastal extension of the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) to better serve coastal users and Member States (MS), and to develop advanced and seamless coastal monitoring and forecasting

systems. FOCCUS uses a combination of remote sensing and in situ data, and numerical models, each improved using AI methods.

More specifically FOCCUS sets out three pillars to pursue this innovative vision:

- to support the exploitation of next generation coastal INS and R/S data and link to hydrology
- to develop the first end-to-end pan-European operational coastal models
- to set the foundation of fully integrated Copernicus and MS coastal systems (MSCS)

These pillars strongly deal with digital data, more specifically they set some “data” goals:

- Physical (PHYS) and biogeochemistry (BGC) essential ocean variables (EOVs) in coastal areas are yet poorly represented in CMEMS
- Real-time or forecast river discharges are not sufficiently used in the model forcing
- Estuarine Box Model (EBMs) are not fully exploited by CMEMS and MSCS to resolve estuary dynamics and to connect to hydrological models
- MSCS are not yet making optimal use of CMEMS data (e.g., satellite data, models), or sufficiently include new modelling technologies

More specifically FOCCUS is going to reuse available data (Copernicus Marine Service and EMODnet), will facilitate the discovery of new in situ data to be linked in and included in both CMEMS and EMODnet in situ (coastal) data collections, will improve the interoperability and the methodology to process these data, will develop/improve models to serve MSCSs users. FOCCUS is not deploying new sensors or platforms and it is not generating new in situ data. FOCUS is developing new models that are going to be included in the CMEMS catalogue and new virtual in situ data (from the EBMs) that will be openly available as soon as possible, as soon as they have been scientifically validated,

Figure 1 shows the FOCCUS structure and addressed goals.

Figure 1. FOCCUS project Work Package structure

Each WP is organised in tasks and each task is either producing, assessing or developing a data/product. In particular, WP2 to WP9 are the data and product generators.

3.2 FOCCUS In Situ Data, EO Observations, and Model Data

As anticipated in the previous section, FOCCUS is organised in WPs and tasks, each (WP2-WP9) task is consuming or producing data products being in one of these three main categories:

1. in situ (INS) observational data
2. satellite derived Earth Observational (EO) products, both new data production and consumption of existing data
3. numerical models (NMO)

The following table summarises this planning:

	INS	EO (producer)	EO (consumer)	NMO
WP2, WP3	x	x	x	
WP4, WP5	x		x	x
WP6, WP7	x		x	x
WP8, WP9	x		x	x

Table 1. Data use details, per WP and expanded below.

In terms of data interoperability & machine-readability, this **D1.2** document sets the general framework and recommendations, while details can be found in the various documents linked and referenced below that are specific to each WP and their use of data.

In WP2 “New insight of high-resolution coastal observations” and WP3 “Validation and Implementation of high-resolution coastal observations”, FOCCUS aims to improve pan-European innovative coastal observations in response to society and EU policy needs in the context of climate change. The improvement of the pan-European innovative coastal observations will then be assessed. Details are given in the table below:

WP	2 and 3
Partner	HEREON, CLS, SOCIB, CNR, NERSC, MET.NO, +ATLANTIC, MHD, BC, DMI, Ifremer, SSBE
Contact person and email	Emma Reyes (ereyes@socib.es) and Antonio Bonaduce (antonio.bonaduce@nersc.no)

Dataset name / brief description	<p>In WP2/3 novel remote-sensing data products will be designed and validated to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -characterise: essential climate variables (such as sea level, sea surface temperature, sea ice change) -enhance weather and marine services (e.g. surface ocean currents) -monitor ocean health and ecosystem (biogeochemical anomalies and trends, seagrass and macroalgae) and -monitor coastal changes (shoreline positions). <p>Data-fusion techniques will be employed to merge remote-sensing and in-situ data, providing improved estimates of coastal ocean circulation, harmful algal blooms (HABs), and inland-marine water connectivity.</p> <p>Additionally, new functionalities, algorithms and AI techniques will be developed and tested to improve the quality of coastal observations (e.g., beach morphodynamics) and the traceability of coastal in-situ and river data.</p> <p>Detailed in the deliverable D2.1 (section 3)</p>
Preexisting or generated in FOCCUS?	Generated, developed and/or improved in FOCCUS
If already existing, DOI or link	NA
Purpose, target user	Detailed in the deliverable D2.1 (section 4)
in situ, remote sensing, model?	In-situ observations, remote sensing, ML model
Data source (instrument, sensor, model short name, samples: sampler, analysis instrument)	Sentinel-6A HR mode, SWOT, Sentinel 3, Sentinel 3, SAR, Sentinel-1A/B SAR, Landsat, multi-platform observations
Level of processing and description	Detailed in the deliverable D2.1 (section 4)
Variables and units	Detailed in the deliverable D2.1 (section 4)
Expected accuracy of data (description for each variable)	To be detailed in the deliverable D3.1 (see Annex)
Link to expected accuracy of data (es. datasheet of the sensor)	To be detailed in the deliverable D3.1 (see Annex)

Spatial extent and resolution	Detailed in the deliverable D2.1 (section 3)
Time span and resolution	Detailed in the deliverable D2.1 (section 3)
Metadata provided	Detailed in the deliverable D2.1 (section 4)
File format	Detailed in the deliverable D2.1 (sections 2 and 3)
applied vocabularies / conventions	Detailed in the deliverable D2.1 (section 4)
link to product	Detailed in the deliverable D2.1 (sections 1 and 2)

In WP4 “Design of improved model interfaces in the Land-Ocean Continuum” and WP5 “Building, validation and demonstration of improved model interfaces in the Land-Ocean Continuum”, FOCCUS aims at improving hydrological modelling (E-HYPE and LISFLOOD) , estuarine models (i.e. upgrades of physics and ML based Estuary Box Model, learning dataset by unstructured grid to support EBM training, EO satellite to support EBM testing) and land-sea boundary conditions targeting improvements of estuarine dynamics and representation of river discharge at the riverine outlets. Hydrological models will be improved through integration of nutrient and sediment transport, which sources are estimated from European databases and calibrated to instream water quality observations. Other foreseen upgrades entail the merging of physical and ML/AI-based approaches for estuarine dynamics and better coupling techniques at river mouths. In WP5 the advancements of the hydrological and estuarine models will be implemented and validated in regional and coastal models across the EU Copernicus Marine Service domain, using EMODnet near-real time data and EO satellite data in both estuarine and plume areas. Details are given in the table below:

WP	4 and 5
Partner	SMHI, CMCC, DMI, +ATLANTIC, DELTARES, HEREON, CNR, MHD, MET.NO,
Contact person and email	Alena Bartosova (alena.bartosova@smhi.se) and Giorgia Verri (giorgia.verri@cmcc.it)
Dataset name / brief description	Base time series with freshwater inputs to coasts (volume flux, physical tracers as temperature and salinity , nutrients, sediment) for current and improved hydrological models and by adding an estuarine box model downstream of the hydrology ones to solve the estuarine water exchange at the net releases at river mouths
Preexisting or generated in FOCCUS?	Preexisting, improved and/or new products within FOCCUS

If already existing, DOI or link	
Purpose, target user	Inputs for regional to coastal models
in situ, remote sensing, model?	model
Data source (instrument, sensor, model short name, samples: sampler, analysis instrument)	model (E-HYPE, LISFLOOD) 1D ML-based Estuary Box Model 3D physically based finite element model (SHYFEM)
Level of processing and description	
Variables and units	Volume flux (m ³ /s), temperature (celsius degree),), salinity (psu), nutrients and sediment (weight / volume, alt. weight / time step)
Expected accuracy of data (description for each variable)	Described in deliverable D4.2
Link to expected accuracy of data (es. datasheet of the sensor)	N/A
Spatial extent and resolution	Described in deliverable D4.2
Time span and resolution	Described in deliverable D4.2
Metadata provided	Described in deliverable D4.2
File format	text file, netCDF
applied vocabularies / conventions	
link to product	

In WP6 “Implementation of new interfaces and methodologies in coastal systems” and WP7 “Coastal Modelling Systems - validation and demonstration”, FOCCUS targets seamless modelling capabilities of the pan-European coasts, from land to open ocean, through the integration of existing Copernicus products into the different Member State Coastal modelling System (MSCS). These data include both numerical and observational data, the former being principally used to force MSCS while the latter being principally used for data assimilation or for MSCS validation. Improvements of the MSCS themselves are also targeted, including ML/AI-assisted methods or ensemble approaches, and the added value of these new types of data for decision support and other stakeholders needs will be assessed. Details are given in the table below:

WP	6 and 7
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Partner	MET.NO, DELTARES, +ATLANTIC, SHOM, RBINS, HEREON, SMHI, CMCC, DMI, MOi, MHD, CNR, NERSC, SOCIB
Contact person and email	Kai Håkon Christensen (kaihc@met.no) and Quentin Jamet (quentin.jamet@shom.fr)
Dataset name / brief description	Data delivery from several coastal systems, as detailed in inventory. Main outputs are physical variables such as salinity, temperature, mean surface heights, ocean currents. For this plan, we restrict ourselves to variables that are specifically addressed in FOCCUS tasks.
Preexisting or generated in FOCCUS?	Preexisting.
If already existing, DOI or link	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Purpose, target user	General public and MSCS downstream decision support systems.
in situ, remote sensing, model?	Model.
Data source (instrument, sensor, model short name, samples: sampler, analysis instrument)	See MSCS inventory (see Annex).
Level of processing and description	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Variables and units	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Expected accuracy of data (description for each variable)	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Link to expected accuracy of data (es. datasheet of the sensor)	N/A
Spatial extent and resolution	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Time span and resolution	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Metadata provided	Yes
File format	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
applied vocabularies / conventions	CF compliant
link to product	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).

In WP8 “Design of Coastal Applications” and WP9 “Building, validation and demonstration of Coastal Applications”, FOCCUS aims to evaluate the improvements made with respect to coastal observations, land-ocean coupling (hydrology), and modelling interfaces for coastal applications along the identified key Environmental and Societal Challenges. WP8 and WP9 will therefore incorporate the improved data products delivered in WP2-WP7. The coastal applications are local configurations of the member state coastal systems that require initial conditions, forcing fields, boundary conditions, river inputs but also independent observations for calibration and validation (in situ and satellite). These inputs originate from various data providers. The coastal applications produce numerical model outputs in the form of time series, two- or three-dimensional environmental fields or aggregate statistics such as fluxes. The model outputs are either distributed in their raw netCDF data formats or post-processed into information services, such as figures, tables, and textual summary. Details are given in the table below:

WP	8 and 9
Partner	CMCC, DELTARES, RBINS, CNR, HEREON, MHD, BC, MET.NO, NERSC, SHOM, MOI, DMI, +ATLANTIC, SOCIB
Contact person and email	Ivan Federico (ivan.federico@cmcc.it) and Lorinc Meszaros (lorinc.meszaros@deltares.nl)
Dataset name / brief description	Coastal Applications: The coastal applications are organised in three groups addressing environmental and societal challenges. The first group of applications aims at supporting better management and protection of the coastal area against pollution and coastal erosion; The second group of applications aims at supporting multi-use of coastal and offshore operations with early warning systems for risks associated to for e.g. HABs, pathogens in aquaculture and cascade impacts from offshore installations; The third group of applications aims at supporting resilience to climate change through for e.g. NBS (seagrass restoration) and prevent natural and anthropogenic hazards and extreme events (e.g. MHWs and storm surges).
Preexisting or generated in FOCCUS?	Preexisting, improved and/or new products within FOCCUS: New products based on pre-existing models (WP6-7), new observation data (WP2-3), improved hydrological data (WP4-5).
If already existing, DOI or link	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).

Purpose, target user	Coastal applications seek to better address the selected Environmental and Societal Challenges: ESC 1 (“Better Manage and Protect the Coastal Area.”), ESC 2 (“Enhance the Blue Economy.”) and ESC 3 (“Natural and Anthropogenic Hazards and Building Resilience to Climate Change”). Target users: MSCS operators with reference users community linked to climate, weather and marine services, ocean health and ocean changes.
in situ, remote sensing, model?	All these features are combined in the coastal applications.
Data source (instrument, sensor, model short name, samples: sampler, analysis instrument)	Data sources for FOCCUS coastal applications combine data sources used for WP6/7 (see MSCS inventory), WP4/5 (Land Ocean models; E-HYPE, LISFLOOD, 1D ML-based Estuary Box Model, 3D physically based finite element model, SHYFEM), WP2/3 (observation data; Sentinel-6A HR mode, SWOT, Sentinel 3, Sentinel 3, SAR, Sentinel-1A/B SAR, Landsat, multi-platform observations).
Level of processing and description	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Variables and units	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Expected accuracy of data (description for each variable)	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Link to expected accuracy of data (es. datasheet of the sensor)	N/A
Spatial extent and resolution	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Time span and resolution	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
Metadata provided	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
File format	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).
applied vocabularies / conventions	CF compliant
link to product	To be detailed in deliverable D9.2 (see Annex).

3.3 Data in Coastal Systems Inventory

As part of the publicly available Milestone **MS6.1** Interfaces Roadmap (see [Annex](#)), existing uses of data in MS Coastal Systems are inventoried and roadmaps of each MS Coastal System have been created for their future development.

- The inventory can be found in the shared project folder here: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1JxFKYBhboVHDFwAgmMikijJ_9N2UFUu6xNmFOAGB21M/edit?usp=sharing (see [Annex](#))
- The roadmaps can be found in the shared project folder here: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1tlmc7NZxheF69ls86elyiv3eLRsgggPH?usp=drive_link (see [Annex](#))

3.4 Data Types and Data Formats

As anticipated, FOCCUS is developing new tools to enhance the coastal extension of Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) to better serve coastal users and Member States (MS), thereby FOCCUS adopts the CMEMS data types and formats. CMEMS is a key element for developing the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EDITO), which extends the CMEMS and EMODnet data format to have prompt virtual high-resolution, multi-dimensional, near-real-time representation of the physical, chemical, biological and socio-economic dimensions of the ocean.

The vast majority of Copernicus Marine products are produced in NetCDF format (.nc). With the entry into service of the new CMEMS Marine Data Store, the infrastructure also supports cloud based formats such as Zarr. Other important file formats for the FOCCUS scope are GeoTIFF and Shapefile data.

The NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) format is a self-describing, platform-independent binary data format commonly used for storing and sharing scientific data, particularly in fields such as climate science, meteorology, oceanography, and geophysics. NetCDF files are designed to be flexible, efficient, and portable, making them suitable for handling large volumes of multidimensional data. As described above, all Copernicus Marine products are delivered in NetCDF-4 format by default. Notably, NetCDF is also the recommended data format for the in situ observational data by both CMEMS INSTAC and EMODnet.

The Zarr format is a Python library and file format designed for efficient storage and manipulation of multi-dimensional array data. Zarr is particularly well-suited for handling large-scale scientific datasets, especially in the context of parallel and distributed computing. This is a key data format to facilitate uninhibited flow of data to the EU Digital Twin Ocean initiative (EU DTO) - EDITO data lake (<https://www.edito.eu/>).

The GeoTIFF format, short for Georeferenced Tagged Image File Format, is a type of raster image file that contains spatially referenced information, making it suitable for use in Geographic Information System (GIS) applications and remote sensing analysis.

The Shapefile format is a popular geospatial vector data format developed by Esri (Environmental Systems Research Institute) for storing and exchanging geographic data in a simple, non-topological format.

EDITO adds the GRIB (GRIdded Binary) that is a widely used data format for meteorological and ocean forecast, HD5 (Hierarchical Data Format) largely used for complex hierarchical data structures, including satellite data, Parquet which is designed for cloud-native and big data environments for improving performance, scalability, and integration with modern cloud analytics.

3.5 Data Storage and Data Access

Project documents such as deliverables, Periodic Reports, and other documents related to the project activities are stored and managed in the dedicated project Google Drive. These are worked collaboratively using the project’s dedicated Google Drive framework, and saved on the shared folders before being also submitted as PDF documents in the EU Portal website.

Additionally, all project deliverables which are public are also submitted on the project’s **Zenodo repository**, under the FOCCUS Community (see dedicated WP sections below for details):

<https://zenodo.org/communities/foccus-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10>.

This ensures: Long-term preservation, DOI assignment for citation, version control, and usage tracking. Zenodo was selected for its alignment with open science practices and its integration with the FOCCUS data infrastructure.

The repository includes NetCDF, CSV, and SHP formats (as well as compressed formats e.g. zip). Access is open unless otherwise stated; restricted datasets are available to FOCCUS partners upon request.

WP	Specific data storage and access considerations
WP1	Access to the project Google Drive is maintained by invitation from the Project Management team, with only project Consortium members able to access the documents before they are published publicly on Zenodo and submitted to the EU Commission for review.
WP2/3	The access details for the data products developed within WP2 are provided in deliverable D2.2 , which includes a comprehensive Table 1 listing each dataset, its coverage, format, version, and the corresponding data access link (DOI).
WP4/5	WP4 datasets are provided in the deliverable D4.1 , consisting of preliminary historical model outputs from the E-HYPE and LISFLOOD models. Data can be accessed via the following links using the Open Science Framework platform:

	<p>E-HYPE: <u>URL:</u> https://osf.io/pr9xh/?view_only=0a7d818627824f15954307eb2cd2d158 <u>ACCESS:</u> Available at OSF storage using the link, however the link itself is not to be shared publicly.</p> <p>LISFLOOD: GREEN: <u>URL:</u> https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1QGBycR2wB8UCkiug3R6h-ydSeMq8ueUO?usp=drive_link <u>ACCESS:</u> Sharing of GREEN nutrient data is limited to project members. The full dataset will be published open-access in JRC Data Catalogue (Water Pressure Indicators collection) at this URL: https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/wpi - expected release date September 2025. LISLOOD river discharge data are available in the Copernicus data repository: https://ewds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/efas-historical?tab=download</p> <p>The detailed description of the both models' structure, set up, used data, calibration approach and particularities are provided in the deliverable D4.2. The datasets are given in NetCDF (.nc), CSV (.csv) format, text file (.txt) and shapefile formats, and are stored on both the shared project Google Drive and the shared project folder on the Open Science Framework (OSF) platform. Metadata files are also stored in addition to the datasets, and metadata are described in this document in detail. Updated and finalized datasets will be provided further during WP5.</p>
WP6/7	<p>There are two main types of output from these WPs: software (processing scripts etc.) and model output data. The first category is central to D6.2 (see Annex), M6.2 (see Annex), and M6.3 (see Annex), and although software will at least partially be available through open repositories elsewhere, a copy of all software will be stored in the project Zenodo repository, which is planned to be integrated with GitHub. A separate short D6.2 report is simultaneously in preparation, which will contain a complete list of software and data as well as access links.</p> <p>Model output data will as a rule be hosted at the producing institutes. In general, model output data produced as part of the WP6/7 activities are not of interest to others than the producing institutions,</p>

	and hence it is primarily data produced for the demonstrators in WP8/9 that will be relevant to share openly.
WP8/9	During the development, demonstration and validation phase, the numerical model outputs produced by the coastal applications are hosted at the producing institutes (WP8/9 partners). Currently, the commonly used storage solutions are internal project drives. The final outcome of these applications will be made accessible within the European Digital Twin Ocean (EDITO) that is designed to integrate ocean numerical models into the EU public infrastructure of the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EDITO-Infra) and providing access to focus applications and simulations of what-if scenarios for the sustainable management of marine environments. The developed scenarios will be included in the EDITO catalogue after their internal validation: the final validated coastal application data outputs will be produced between Month 32-36, in line with D9.1 (see Annex), D9.2 (see Annex), and will be made available by Month 36 as described in Milestone MS9.3 (see Annex) - Demonstration assessment (means of verification: “Files available on project workspace”). For each of the model output a describing item will be listed in the project Zenodo catalogue. Inclusion of the coastal application outcomes in the EDITO catalogue also means that users can directly visualize them in the advanced EDITO viewer .
WP10/11	This WP includes additional maintenance of the project website, which is detailed in deliverable D10.1 .

3.6 Data Quality

The platform data.europa.eu (i.e. the official portal for European Union (EU) data) has recently published the data quality guidelines for delivering high-quality open data. These recommendations are directed at data providers to support them in preparing their data, developing their data strategy and ensuring data quality.

FOCCUS is adopting these recommendations and in particular is applying measures for making data FAIR, using, as described in this document, well known and standardised data models and formats, using common vocabularies and standards (ISO and community defined dictionaries), adopting easy data access and data download tools.

Moreover, all data collected and produced in FOCCUS will refer/document the applied (scientific) methodology (citation of references). The following data quality principles will be applied:

3.6.1 Data Quality Principles

The principles aim to encourage all involved in research to maintain, and to respond adequately to possible threats or violations of research integrity. FOCCUS researchers should be guided by these principles at each stage of the project work and in particular they have to ensure:

3.6.1.1 Academic Excellence

Researchers have to apply sound methodology, suitable methods, standard procedures and documented protocols where appropriate, to ensure the highest quality of work, its dissemination and replicability.

3.6.1.2 Honesty

Researchers must acknowledge the direct and indirect contributions of colleagues, collaborators and others. The basic principle of any scientific activity is the need for researchers to be honest in respect of their own actions and in their responses to the actions of other scientists.

3.6.1.3 Accountability

Researchers should recognise their responsibility to the general public, and should take all reasonable measures to ensure that their research complies with any agreement, related policies and professional bodies' guidance; and allows for proper governance and transparency.

3.6.1.4 Care and Respect

Researchers should avoid any unreasonable risk or harm to research subjects and researchers themselves.

3.6.2 Data Traceability

In line with the above described principles, FOCCUS is adopting all necessary measures to ensure data traceability, and approaches this by using the combination of Zenodo and ORCID. In all aspects of research, substantive contributions of formal collaborators and all others who directly assist or indirectly support the research must be properly acknowledged.

This applies to any circumstances in which statements about the research are made, including provision of information about the nature and process of the research, and in publishing the outcome. Failure to acknowledge the contributions of others is regarded as unethical conduct. For facilitating the traceability of the authors, FOCCUS encourages the use of ORCID (<https://orcid.org/>).

This also applies to data and data products that are going to be (re)used in the project and is achieved by documenting the sources and the methods (references, DOI, or any other identifier whenever available/applicable). The use of a Zenodo repository also enables data traceability. Each of the FOCCUS products will be registered in the FOCCUS catalogue (FOCCUS Zenodo community) that permits to associate the product to a unique id. Sources, processing methodologies, other pre-existing rights will be listed in the product

description/quality document (the CMEMS products already apply similar strategy by offering QUID and PUM for each of the product)¹

It also applies data products that are collected and produced by FOCCUS by properly documenting and by assigning a DOI to each of them.

Updates are considered updated versions of the document and/or data. The integration of DOIs further ensures that the project output and all methodology is documented and organized throughout the course of the project and beyond.

3.7 Data Collected from Stakeholders

In FOCCUS, responses from different stakeholder surveys will be used and additional surveys could be developed to co-design FOCCUS R&I and to gather needs from stakeholders (WP10-WP11).

These data will be handled following the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

3.8 Data Utility Outside the Project

FOCCUS (Forecasting and Observing the Open-to-Coastal Ocean for Copernicus Users) is part of the 2023 Horizon Europe calls for Space supervised by HaDEA, the Health and Digital Executive Agency, and aims at enhancing the Copernicus Marine Service's existing capabilities and developing innovative coastal monitoring and forecasting products. This includes changes in the use of new space and in situ coastal observations, innovations in data fusion, data processing and visualisation, together with seamless numerical forecasting from regional models of the Copernicus Marine Service covering the EU regional seas, to Member States coastal forecasting systems

Coastal zones have large social, economic and environmental values. They are more densely populated than the hinterland and concentrate large economic assets, critical infrastructures and human activities such as tourism, fisheries, navigation. Furthermore, the coastal ocean is home to a wealth of living marine resources and very productive ecosystems. Yet, coastal zones are exposed to various natural and anthropogenic hazards, such as pollution, eutrophication, and habitat degradation. Natural hazards can be exacerbated by climate change and induced ocean warming, acidification, deoxygenation, sea level rise, increases in harmful algae blooms and invasive species.

While Europe has a robust capability for ocean monitoring, particularly through the Copernicus Marine Service, the use of Earth observation (EO) data for coastal monitoring is not fully explored. The FOCCUS project aims to enhance the Copernicus Marine Service's coastal dimension by fostering collaboration between European Research and Innovation

¹e.g. <https://documentation.marine.copernicus.eu/QUID/CMEMS-GLO-QUID-001-024.pdf>, <https://documentation.marine.copernicus.eu/PUM/CMEMS-GLO-PUM-001-024.pdf>

entities (R&I), public authorities (including coastal services) and industry stakeholders. This involves producing coastal information through the creation of new computational models utilising data from both MSCS and the Copernicus Marine Service for improved monitoring and forecasting of coastal zones.

The initiative aligns with EU policies, including the European Green Deal, and contributes to global efforts such as the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development.

Regarding user training and guidance on how to use FOCCUS data products, these are to be taken into consideration in the second phase of the project to ensure adequate user engagement and uptake.

3.9 Data - Risk Management

In line with the FOCCUS project's commitment to open science and FAIR data principles, risk management for data-related issues is a critical aspect of ensuring the reliability, integrity, and continuity of data handling throughout the project lifecycle.

The following categories outline key risks and corresponding mitigation strategies identified within the scope of FOCCUS data management activities:

3.9.1. Data Loss or Corruption

Risk: Accidental loss or corruption of datasets due to system failures, human error, or cyberattacks.

Mitigation: data storage is performed across multiple services, including partners' infrastructure and Zenodo. Partners data servers do backup periodically according to internal policies.

3.9.2. Incomplete Metadata or Documentation

Risk: Datasets may be rendered less useful or non-reusable due to missing metadata or poor documentation.

Mitigation: Adoption of ISO 19115 and other community metadata standards as described in deliverable **D2.1**. Implementation of metadata validation and pre-submission quality checks at WP level.

3.9.3. GDPR and Ethical Non-compliance

Risk: Mishandling of personal data from stakeholder surveys or non-compliance with GDPR could result in legal issues.

Mitigation: All stakeholder-related data are anonymised and processed in compliance with the FOCCUS GDPR framework (Milestone **MS1.1**, see [Annex](#)). Consent forms, risk registers, and audit trails are maintained and reviewed periodically.

3.9.4. Interoperability and Compatibility Failures

Risk: Data formats or standards used within FOCCUS may be incompatible with external platforms or stakeholders' needs.

Mitigation: Standardisation of data formats (NetCDF, Zarr, GeoTIFF, etc.) and controlled vocabularies (CF conventions, GCMD keywords, etc) as described in deliverable **D2.1**.

Engagement with Copernicus Marine Service, EMODnet, EDITO, and OceanPrediction DCC ensures compatibility alignment.

3.9.5. Limited Data Reusability or Visibility

Risk: FOCCUS datasets may not be effectively reused if they are difficult to discover or lack sufficient dissemination.

Mitigation: All datasets are deposited in searchable repositories with assigned DOIs. Active dissemination through FOCCUS portal, Zenodo, and integration into CMEMS services and catalogues (e.g. Copernicus Coastal Hub). Clear documentation and citation guidance are provided with each dataset.

Moreover the FOCCUS project designed and is managing a risk table where the Likelihood (low, medium, high) and Severity (low, medium, high) define the Risk Index (ranging from 1-9), where $RI = L * S$

Description of risk	WPs	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	R-Index
Partners leave, long-term illness of key staff, change of roles or poor partner performance and conflicts. Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium	ALL	Partners will notify the issue and/or the conflict, to be solved as defined in the Consortium Agreement. Close monitoring of all activities will mitigate the risk. PC and WP co-leaders are tenured staff. All partners have qualified personnel.	2
Project personnel leave, team composition change, barriers to effective teamwork. Likelihood: Low Severity: Low	ALL	Comprehensive and updated documentation since the very beginning of the project would help to reduce risks in the project development.	1
Delay in the recruitment of the personnel. Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium	ALL	Internationally open, efficient, transparent recruitment strategy and worldwide advertising will speed the hiring process.	2

<p>Management difficulties due to the large consortia, problems lead to delay of deliverables or project activities.</p> <p>Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium</p>	WP1	FOCCUS R has clear management structure and procedure. s, WP co-leaders, SCT and ExC members have long-standing experience in EU programs of comparable size. The project management platform will ensure effective management	2
<p>Short/long-time breakdown of satellite data or poor data quality.</p> <p>Likelihood: Low Severity: Low</p>	WP2	Work with similar observations and or simulated observations.	1
<p>Significant reduction in the observation spatio-temporal coverage due to upstream processing chain failure.</p> <p>Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium</p>	WP2 WP3	Inform in case of degradation of the product quality. Strategic European coastal areas will be selected based on critical pre-observed coastal patterns and data availability.	2
<p>Delay in the delivery of the first sample files needed for other WPs.</p> <p>Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium</p>	WP2 - WP7	Similar data products will be proposed to start the other WPs work. Regular meetings with the downstream/upstream WPs will be held to check the progress and the needs.	2
<p>Failure to calibrate E-HYPE with added nutrient and sediment routines.</p> <p>Likelihood: Medium Severity: Low</p>	WP4 WP5	Because the proposed E-HYPE development work takes an incremental approach based on a well-developed base model, we can adapt calibration targets as the project develops and thereby minimize the risk of unsuccessful calibration.	2
<p>Failure to perform the LISFLOOD calibration and set up and calibrate LISFLOOD with added nutrient and sediment routines.</p> <p>Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium</p>	WP4 WP5	The proposed LISFLOOD development will be performed by CMCC and JRC (external collaboration); the planned work will be executed by CMCC scientists including visits at JRC and joint meetings and workshops. The work is based on the well developed LISFLOOD open source model. CMCC in collaboration with JRC will be able to adapt to upcoming challenges and to implement model improvements successfully.	2
<p>Scarce availability of river runoff, PHYS (salinity, temperature), nutrients and sediments in-situ data in the estuary coastal areas for testing purposes.</p> <p>Likelihood: Medium Severity: Medium</p>	WP3- WP5	Strategic European coastal areas have been selected based on critical pre-observed data availability. Unstructured grid models will be used to estimate PHYS variables in the estuary and calibrate the EBM model.	4
<p>Collaboration with JRC being external to the project will not work as expected.</p> <p>Likelihood:Low Severity:High</p>	WP4 WP[1] 5	CMCC/JRC meetings have been carried out before the submission to plan activities. CMCC will notify any issue to the PC and ExC to discuss the mitigation measures.	3
<p>Issues with technical implementation of interfaces CMEMS/MSCS.</p> <p>Likelihood: Low</p>	WP6 WP7	MSCSs already have well-established data streams and production chains. Tight coordination will be used to ensure progress to meet planned deliveries.	2

Severity: Medium			
Issues with delivery of observation data. Likelihood: Medium Severity: High	WP6 WP7	Divert the task efforts to another observation type from WP2-3 (surface currents). No consequence for demonstrations.	6
Technical problems with MSCSs preventing completion of planned tests. Likelihood: Medium Severity: Low	WP6 WP7	Tests will be done at TRL 5-6 and do not require 24/7 operational capacity, hence providing more flexibility w.r.t. execution.	4
Insufficient feedback from Member States and reference user communities. Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium	WP8 WP9	Early and regular engagement of Member states and reference user communities.	2
Requirements of Member States and reference user communities are not completely fulfilled. Likelihood: Medium Severity: Medium	WP9, WP8	Establishment and active engagement with the National Marine Stakeholder Forum to iteratively validate requirements.	4
Delay in the implementation of applications, Likelihood: Medium Severity: Medium	WP8 WP9	Defining a milestone (MS9.1) for the prototypes well ahead of the final versions.	4
Diverging or overly demanding needs collected during the co-design thematic workshops. Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium	WP10	MOi will assist all co-design workshops and work to translate user needs into achievable specifications for the technical WPs.	2
Lack of participation in workshop events. Likelihood: Low Severity: Low	WP10 WP11	All workshops will be online enabling an inclusive participation and to maximise attendance. In addition there can be flexibility in re-scheduling the workshop, if required.	1
Lack of wider stakeholder awareness about the project and/or failure of the planned communication and dissemination activities. Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium	WP10 WP11	There will be a clear, step-wise and multi-channelled communication and dissemination plan, that will deliver fit-for-use public tools e.g., website and outputs e.g., brochure, video to engage the key stakeholder groups of the project. The status of stakeholder engagement will be assessed to finetune and optimise further stakeholder onboarding and engagement.	2
Low uptake in Copernicus Marine and Member States services. Likelihood: Low Severity: Medium	WP11	The uptake into the Copernicus Marine Service will be carefully planned, organized and (D11.2). MOi, EE by the EC for the implementation of CMEMS, will oversee the strategic alignment and the transferability of FOCCUS' outcomes to CMEMS.	2

These risks and measures are reviewed whenever needed and integrated in the next version of the DMP.

4. FAIR Data

Over the last three decades great progress was made at European level in terms of advancing these standards and facilitating machine-to-machine data processing, and programs and projects such as Copernicus Marine Service, EMODnet, SeaDataNet, H2020 EuroSea etc are continuously updating these recommendations (see Tanhua et al. 2019 for an exhaustive review).

FORCE11 broke down the FAIR recommendations into 15 characteristics to facilitate FAIR principle understanding, implementation and assessment. The following table summarizes how FOCCUS is implementing its FAIR strategy.

Findable		Evidence
F1	(meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier	FOCCUS is using the Zenodo community to assign a DOI to each dataset
F2	data are described with rich metadata	Table 1 offers more specific links
F3	(meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	Zenodo community represents a primary project catalogue. In parallel FOCCUS data and products are included under CMEMS and EMODnet catalogues
F4	metadata specify the data identifier	the DOI is listed in the metadata
Accessible		
A1	(meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol	Yes, each FOCCUS data and data product has an entry under the Zenodo community that offers direct access to retrieve the digital object
A1.1	the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	Yes, and licence is CC-BY
A1.2	the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	Yes, FOCCUS products are open, public available and consumable according CMEMS, EMODnet and EDITO specifications see also par 4.2
A2	metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	Zenodo community ensures long term preservation of metadata and data
Interoperable		
I1	(meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation	Yes, see Data Format section

I2	(meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	FOCCUS adopts the community and stakeholders' vocabularies for easy and immediate use of FOCCUS outcomes
I3	(meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	See Table 1 for details
Reusable		
R1	(meta)data have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	yes, links in Table 1 provide full details
R1.1	(meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence	yes, FOCCUS adopts CC-BY by default
R1.2	(meta)data are associated with their provenance	yes, links in Table 1 provide full details
R1.3	(meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	yes, links in Table 1 provide full details

Table 2. FAIR principles proposed by the FORCE11 community.

Notably, these recommendations always include three main elements for implementing interoperability: metadata (including data quality), data format, and data services.

More specifically, according to our Grant Agreement (Art. 187), metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (particularly machine-actionable), and must provide information on at least the following:

- Title
- Date of publication
- Publication venue
- Horizon Europe funding: HORIZON-CL4-2023-SPACE-01
- Grant project name, acronym, and number: FOCCUS, Funded by the European Union, Grant Agreement No. 101133911
- Licensing terms
- Persistent identifiers for the publication
- Authors involved in the action (preferably using ORCID) and, if possible, their organisations (preferably using the PIC and EDMO code)

The usability of data and outcomes strongly depends on the data policy license. There is an increasing push for adopting the Creative Commons framework, particularly the CC-BY license (the only limitation being that credit must be given to the creator).

Embargoes on data and other CC licenses can also be applied where the policy is 'As open as possible, as closed as necessary'. Partners can avoid offering open access in two cases:

- 1) If open access would be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including commercial exploitation
- 2) If open access would be contrary to any other constraints, particularly the EU's competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement

If open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP (as annex).

Going narrower into the dataset/product description, according to the ISO-19115, the minimum set of metadata to ensure comprehensive identification of the dataset/product has to include its spatial dimension, temporal dimension, depth, source and quality control for each element.

For the spatial dimension, the WGS84 standard must be used to uniform the applicability across the globe. For the temporal dimension, the ISO 8601 standard must be used, which provides a clear and consistent format for representing dates and times. The vocabulary used in keywords should be consistent with the GCMD to ensure consistency and facilitate data discovery.

For the parameters and units, the Copernicus Marine Service conventions should be applied.

4.1 Data Licence Statement

FOCCUS is an EU supported research project, hence all the collected data have to be freely available to the community at no cost and limitation. As described, in FOCCUS, all contributions will be Open Access and data will be openly available with licences following the CC BY 4.0 "unrestricted" standard (or equivalent), while metadata will follow the CC 0 licence (see previous section).

Digital data will be made available through the Copernicus Marine Service.

While pre-existing rights are indicated in the Consortium Agreement, forward intellectual rights are based on the real contribution to the development of the new products. Considering that all the products are going to be publically available (CC-BY) the IPRs are limited to clear citation of the team and the project that has developed the knowledge. Downstream application, commercial use, adoption between partners of the developed products are fully allowed and do not generate any fee.

FOCCUS is committed to develop open science hence any user should be able to replicate the same results by using the same tools and operating the same data/products.

According to the UE definition an open software in research is a software made available with a license that grants freedom to run, study, modify, share (code and modifications). Well known platforms to share and preserve code are GitHub, Bitbucket, SourceForge. The combination of e.g. Zenodo and GitHub to archive releases, automatically generate DOIs, and ensure long-term accessibility and elevate the openness of the project results.

Notably the combination of Zenodo and Github can also be considered for overcoming limitations of repositories to host models code and model outputs.

4.2 Other Actions to Make FOCCUS Data/Products FAIR

FOCCUS outcomes would be either included into the CMEMS Data Store and listed into the CMEMS catalogue (<https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/products>) or may be presented and described as CMEMS Use Cases (<https://marine.copernicus.eu/services/use-cases>).

Moreover, FOCCUS project partners are encouraged to contribute their models to the DCC repository using the form provided on the OceanPrediction DCC website, ensuring that they are accessible to the wider ocean prediction community.

OceanPrediction DCC website - <https://www.unoceanprediction.org/en/atlas/models>

The OceanPrediction Decade Collaborative Centre (DCC) is emerging as a key initiative within the European Union's strategic actions for ocean science and sustainable development. In line with the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, this European initiative, hosted by Mercator Ocean International, represents a concerted effort to harness collective expertise and resources to achieve a sustainable global ocean by 2030. Incorporating models into the work of the DCC can provide powerful ocean prediction capabilities around the world, widening FOCCUS stakeholders and facilitating sustainable ocean management practices.

4.3 Assessing FAIR-ness

FOCCUS adopts and adapts the FAIRness metrics developed under FAIR-IMPACT. Notably FAIR is not binary, it is an indicator of progression. For software (and models pipelines are software tools) FAIR-IMPACT suggests 17 questions² to address software fairness:

1. Does the software have a globally unique and persistent identifier?
2. Do the different components of the software have their own identifiers?
3. Does each version of the software have a unique identifier?
4. Does the software include descriptive metadata which helps define its purpose?
5. Does the software include development metadata which helps define its status?
6. Does the software include metadata about the contributing authors and their role?
7. Does the software metadata include the identifier for the software?
8. Does the software have a public, open, accessible, persistent metadata record?
9. Is the software developed in a code repository, so that users can use standard communication processes?
10. Are the formats used by data consumed or produced by the software open and a reference provided to the format?

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10047401>

11. Does the software use an open API that supports machine-readable interface definitions?
12. Does the software provide references to other objects that support its use?
13. Does the software describe what is requested to use it?
14. Does the software come with test cases to demonstrate it is working?
15. Does the software source code include licensing information for the software and any bundled external software?
16. Does the software metadata include licensing information?
17. Does the software include provenance information that describes the development of the software?

FAIR-IMPACT recommends to include the link to the adopted vocabularies and ontologies in the metadata. The FAIR-EASE project conducts analyses across numerous environmental disciplines to ascertain the types of semantic artefacts employed, uncovering several semantic repositories and vocabulary services dedicated to earth science and marine communities. Notably, the marine sector (which FOCCUS belongs to) utilises the NERC Vocabulary Server, as adopted by Copernicus Marine Service, hence FOCCUS.

Table 1 describes the WP outcomes providing the user with the full metadata and adopted standards in the referred documents.

FAIR-IMPACT also suggests tools to assess and improve project outcomes FAIRness, and the F-UJI FAIR assessment tool (<https://www.f-uji.net>) automatically checks how well a research digital object follows FAIR principles. Starting from the object’s DOI or URL and gives score and suggestion to improve FAIR compliance.

By using the F-UJI tool to assess the FAIRness of the FOCCUS digital outcomes published on the Zenodo catalogue, FOCCUS scores 84 out of 88.

Summary:

Figure 2. F-UJI score for the item: <https://zenodo.org/records/14945395> (test conducted on 14/06/2025).

5. Impact

5.1. Contribution to the Project Objectives

The FOCCUS DMP sets the schemes and rules for project data management and sharing. This applies to all project Objectives, but more specifically it is a pillar for the implementation of these initial Objectives:

- Objective 1: Improve pan-European innovative coastal observations in response to society and EU policy needs.
- Objective 2: Improve land-coast-open ocean interfaces.

In the implementation of these Objectives, new coastal data products will be created by the fusion of in situ and remote sensing coastal data and biogeochemical parameters, in addition to hydrological data. This includes an inventory of the current status of coastal data available in different EU marine data services (i.e., CMEMS, EMODnet, JERICO-RI, DANUBIUS-RI) that will be performed allowing the identification of respective gaps. Thereby, the foundation will be laid for further work on MSCS modelling and data fusion, for integration into established CMEMS global/regional systems and production of new applications in Objective 3 and Objective 4.

As described in the previous section, FOCCUS is setting up a data management infrastructure that is adopting and adapting the recommendations and lessons learnt from major European Marine Data initiatives and is interoperable towards both EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service. It applies FAIR principles and implements tools to be INSPIRE compliant.

5.2. Contribution to the Expected Outcomes

The DMP is supporting the FOCCUS data management towards all its EOs.

5.3. Policy Relevance

The FOCCUS Data Management Plan is setting (proposing) a better and more clear schema for data delivery and Commission assessment on the Horizon Europe project data FAIRness, more specifically it is embracing and promoting the adoption of CC and in particularly CC-BY whenever possible, and it is proposing to have clear statements on embargoed data, meaning that some data will may go under embargo for enabling scientific processing and fine tuning (and publication), but since now the project is declaring that all the data will be available and linkable. New observational capacity (modelling and new coastal products) is already declared and at the end of the project it can be easily tracked if and how much the project was compliant to this statement.

Being in contact – cooperating with the major European Marine Data Integrators (EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service) is important to have a further channel to make value of the project data. Some FOCCUS data may be not included in these integrators (because of the scope, type ...) but it is important that the ones that are of interest to those initiatives can easily flow to/interoperate with them. The adoption of open data policy and open science

principles are further cornerstones of this process and should be encouraged as a EU policy for research projects.

5.4. Communication, Dissemination, and Publications

Communication, Dissemination and Publication are reported in the non-public facing document: deliverable **D10.1** Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan.

6. Other Research Outputs

FOCCUS is an ambitious project and there will be several outputs going from new data and products to deliverables, to publications, to dissemination materials. These outputs are planned and this approach matches the open science practices. This document is describing the approach on data and data-products data management approach, while plans for communication strategy, deliverable quality, document management, web and social communication are addressed in other deliverables.

The project's data and data-products are digital objects and they will be published together with (FAIR) metadata, be assigned a digital object identifier (DOI) and be available/linkable in the FOCCUS web portal or web data infrastructure.

7. Allocation of Resources

7.1. Costs Before Making Data or Other Research Outputs FAIR

Besides having a DM team, each partner has some allocated budget to implement fairness according to the principles and recommendations described in this document.

7.2. Responsible for Data Management

Data Management is included in a dedicated project work package (WP1), led by Hereon.

Responsible for the data management is Kelli Johnson (HEREON), who is the Scientific Project Manager for FOCCUS at Hereon, with a background in oceanography and data science.

Considering the complexity of the project, the Data Manager is assisted by a team of experts, with strong background in remote sensing data management, in situ data, and numerical modelling. More specifically, she will be supported by:

Joanna Staneva (HEREON), is a Senior Scientist and Head of the Department "Hydrodynamics and Data Assimilation" at Helmholtz Centre Hereon, Germany. She holds a Diploma in Physics and a PhD in Physical Oceanography from the University of Sofia, Bulgaria. Dr. Staneva has expertise in marine research, research management, and interdisciplinary collaboration. Her work includes modeling the marine environment, earth system modeling,

ocean predictability, climate dynamics, and coastal and regional oceanography. She actively contributes to scientific advancement by coordinating the Horizon Europe project FOCCUS and participating in international and national projects.

Francisco Campuzano (+ATLANTIC), who has been the leader of the EMODnet physics river node and also of operational numerical models in Portugal. He is member of several EuroGOOS working groups where data and model results standard practices were defined and implemented.

Antonio Novellino (ETT, subcontractor of +ATLANTIC), who has long experience in data management and ocean data management and sharing for both Copernicus Marine Service (he was the CMEMS Dissemination Unit deputy), EMODnet (he is the Coordinator of EMODnet Physics, and leader in EMODnet Ingestion operational data ingestion flow), and several H2020 and HEurope marine data and services projects.

Whenever a FOCCUS data product is hosted, safekept into any other well known/TRUSTed repository, WP1 will list the proper links.

7.3. Long Term Preservation

For the duration of the project, data is going to be hosted by the FOCCUS data management infrastructure. This infrastructure is based on the key European integrating data ocean infrastructures and programs (CMEMS, EMODnet) and FOCCUS outcomes will be directly deposited in these long-term safe keeping systems. FOCCUS outcomes will always be visible and identifiable by means of data-products metadata (and citation statement).

8. Data Security

Data security is not a concern for the specific goals of the project: FOCCUS is developing open science and open products that are going to be made available in CC-BY (or equivalent) as soon as possible.

Each partner which is running a service or a code is adopting standard procedures to safekeeping the development (e.g. backup).

The use of Zenodo as a repository for project digital outcomes represents a second level of security.

9. Ethics and GDPR

Ethics and GDPR are covered by the FOCCUS milestone **MS1.1: GDPR-compliant project management portal created, including risk register**. By M3 of the project, the Coordinator communicated with the Project Officer to establish an approved ethical statement which was then circulated amongst the Consortium members with no issues or rejections to complete milestone **MS1.1** (see [Annex](#)).

Furthermore, an Ethics Advisory Committee (EAC) has been established in M16, consisting of the Work Package co-leaders as well as Project Manager and Project Coordinator, serving as representatives from partners involved in each of the Work Packages. This group is committed to discussing bi-monthly ongoing ethics topics, risks, and planning to ensure that ethical standards are adhered to for all aspects of the project.

The EAC has agreed upon the establishment of an ethics framework throughout the project per WP, as part of the overall project governance, to ensure compliance with GDPR, data security, and informed consent. Additionally, this applies to interactions with third parties such as stakeholders or data sources to protect the privacy of all involved in project activities. Part of this strategy encompasses the monitoring of ethical standards and obtaining feedback from stakeholders and reviewers to ensure satisfactory compliance. Mitigation strategies are considered to proactively address ethical risks, ensuring transparency and accountability.

10. Updates of the DMP

This DMP will be updated in month 36.

Annex

Referenced MS1.1 GDPR compliant project management portal created, including risk register:

MS1.1 GDPR compliant project management portal created, including risk register is a milestone which was delivered, following the PO's request before the start of the FOCCUS Project. After communications to refine the ethics statement with the previous Project Officer in the project communication section of the EU Portal, an email with the agreed-upon statement was circulated to Consortium in March 2025, with the request to reply if there were any objections. Email content was as follows:

"Ethics response:

In the course of the organization of meetings, the names and email addresses of the participants will be collected. During recruitments, more detailed personal information (e.g., in the form of CVs) will be collected by the respective partners.

For all partners in the FOCCUS consortium, the following measures are in place to guarantee data protection:

- *Existence of information security and data protection regulations*
- *Obligation of the employees involved in data processing to maintain confidentiality (Art. 28 Para. 3 Sentence 1 Letter b GDPR, Art. 29 GDPR) as well as issuing information on data protection*
- *Data protection training for employees*
- *Instructing employees regarding IT use and information security, data protection and data backup*
- *Determination of responsibilities and responsibilities for devices and systems*
- *Exclusive use of authorized company-owned IT systems or external systems tested by information technology before use*

Regarding the use of AI: The team has not identified any ethical issues surrounding the use of AI in this project, including ethical issues related to human rights and values. The use of AI-based algorithms is for very restricted and clearly defined FOCCUS purposes, namely for improving the quality and to advance coastal observations and models. Therefore, there cannot be any potential discrimination against humans as a result of the system, and the system will not have any potential to lead to negative social or environmental impacts."

This milestone was then recorded as completed in the EU Portal upon the receipt of zero objections.

Referenced D3.1 summary:

D1.3: Data Quality Assessment is a public report that will be due at M30 as part of WP3, and led by partner CLS. This deliverable will consist of Cal/Val reports of data products identified in WP2.

Referenced D6.2 summary:

D6.2: Software Repository of ML and DA Algorithms is a public report that will be due at M18 as part of WP6, and led by partner MET.NO. This deliverable will consist of a software repository of ML and DA algorithms.

Referenced MS6.2 summary:

MS6.2: Nested Models Implemented in a Unified Framework is a milestone that will be due at M18 as part of WP6, and led by partner Deltares. This will be considered achieved when the files are available on project workspaces, and included as a part of D6.2 above.

Referenced MS6.3 summary:

MS6.3: New Observation Operators is a milestone that will be due at M18 as part of WP6, and led by partner MET.NO. To achieve this, the software will be available, with assessment results reported. This will be reported as part of D6.2 above.

Referenced D9.1 summary:

D9.1: Demonstration of Applications is a public pilot/prototype that will be due at M32 as part of WP9, and led by partner Deltares. This deliverable will consist of a demonstration of the coastal applications by running test cases, documented in interactive handbooks.

Referenced D9.2 summary:

D9.2: Assessment of Applications is a public report that will be due at M36 as part of WP9, and led by partner CMCC. This deliverable will consist of an assessment of the coastal applications, including benchmarking, validation metrics, recommendations, verification of KPIs and evaluation of TRL.

Referenced MS9.3 summary:

MS9.3: Demonstration Assessment is a milestone that will be due at M36 as part of WP9, and led by partner Deltares. To achieve this, the software will be available, with assessment results reported. This will be considered achieved when the files are available on project workspaces.

Other documents referenced:

MSCS Inventory:

A preliminary inventory of coastal systems was agreed upon and created by the Consortium during the first year of the project, in order to better organize efforts to achieve the goals laid out in the DoA to improve them. A summary of this document can be found below, as it is not available on the EU Portal or for public dissemination.

Additionally, the Commission has the right to request access to this document directly using the project's shared drive here:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1JxFKYBhboVHDFwAgmMikijJ_9N2UFUu6xNmFOA GB21M/edit?usp=sharing

This inventory includes a list of project partners, their relevant WPs and regions of interest, in addition to details about their coastal systems which are being used and developed in this project per the DoA. This includes the name of the systems, objectives for improvement, models used, current observations and forcing data, and how these systems interface with Copernicus Marine. Additionally, cross-WP connections for each coastal system are listed here, specifically how each has links to hydrology. Links to initial performance metrics for each coastal system are included here, in addition to roadmaps for improving each system's interfacing with Copernicus (detailed further below).

Roadmaps for Improved Interfacing with CMEMS:

As part of milestone MS6.1: Interfaces Roadmap, roadmaps for improving each coastal system's interfacing with Copernicus was created in M6 of the project. A summary of this milestone can be found below, as it is not available on the EU Portal or for public dissemination.

Additionally, the Commission has the right to request access to the documents that make up this milestone directly using the project's shared drive here:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1tlmc7NZxheF69Is86elyiv3eLRsgggPH?usp=drive_link

These roadmaps include a summary of each member state coastal system, the Copernicus Marine model products used, as well as a description of the existing nesting method used. Crucially, these roadmaps detail for each coastal system the proposed improvements in this nesting, and will be used for the work outlined in the DoA in WP6/7.

References

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